

Why nursing care is missed?

Editorial

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Nursing care is an important part for success of clinical therapeutics and diagnosis. The problem of nursing care can be seen elsewhere. An important consideration is on missed nursing care. The common elements of missed nursing care usually lie on these scopes: “ambulation, turning, delayed or missed feedings, patient teaching, discharge planning, emotional support, hygiene, intake and output documentation, and surveillance [5].” The question on “why nursing care is missed?” should be discussed. Blackman et al (2014) noted that “shift type, nursing resource allocation, health professional communication, work load intensity, work load predictability, the nurses' satisfaction with their current job and their intention to remain working” were the factor influencing why nursing care is missed. It is no doubt that missed nursing care is an important issue in clinical nursing. Of interest, the problem seems to be different in different settings. Kalisch et al. (2009) performed a similar study and found some different factors and concluded for the main three things to be considered: “a) antecedents that catalyze the need for a decision about priorities, b) elements of the nursing process and c) internal perceptions and

values of the nurse.”

Since missed nursing care can be serious and leads to several problems, the preventive management is needed. It is suggested that any nursing center should have a system to identify and manage the problem [3]. Also, finding of some supportive tools to prevent missed care is required. A good example is using electronic nursing care reminders [4]. Piscotty Jr and Kalisch (2014) reported for “a significant relationship between nursing care reminders usage and decreased amounts of missed nursing care.” Arditi et al. (2012) noted that using computer generated reminders delivered on paper could moderately help improve in the process of care and the two main predictors of improvement included “providing space on the reminder for a response from the clinician and providing an explanation of the reminder's content or advice.”

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